

Review

Corporate Social Responsibility and Kantian Approach to Business Ethics: An Integrative Framework

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Abstract: The motivation behind this paper is to address the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) issues and to prescribe applied Kantian way of thinking to conceptualize the obligations and duties of an individual with respect to utilization of CSR in corporate administration rehearses. People do have a feeling of obligation and feeling of what is correct and what's up from a moral point of view. There is a requirement for a code of moral practice in business to urge people to apply their feeling of obligation at workers or the board. In this respects, Kant's way of thinking can function as a structure which will give a layout to think about issues in corporate administration from the viewpoint of ethical quality, equity, temperance and legislative issues. The paper opens the discussion on the requirement for a moral establishment or "good measurement" in corporate administration that goes past a public connection work out.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), Kantian

Introduction

Scholastic and business directors have seen how corporate social obligation (CSR) has been changed from a superfluous and far fetched thought to a high-positioning subject on exploration plans (McWilliams et al., 2006). CSR is all the more frequently misconstrued as rewarding the general public and viewed as inseparable from generosity. The prevailing way of thinking is that CSR is no generous movement and a business should procure for what it contributes. The organization does it for its own drawn out great. Drawing a corresponding with Publicity and advertising it is contended that generosity could procure exposure yet CSR, similar to Public Relations is a drawn out speculation with guaranteed returns. It advocates that CSR establishes a

progression of activities taken by an organization in its edified personal circumstance. Along these lines, CSR picked up generally customary and broadly acknowledged ideas in the business world during ongoing years (Carroll and Shabana, 2010). As indicated by Lee (2008), conceptualizations of and research on CSR have developed along two roads:

1. In terms of the level of analysis, researchers have moved from a discussion of the macro social effects to an organizational-level analysis of CSR and its impact on organizational processes and performance; and
2. In terms of the theoretical orientation of this field, researchers have shifted from explicitly normative and ethics-oriented arguments to implicitly normative and performance-oriented managerial studies.

In this paper, we advance the idea of a code of ethical practice that is more than an ethical mission statement of intent characteristic of modern companies. It is also discussed in Duran and McNutt (2010). A code of ethical practice is an agreed code of duties and responsibilities that when adopted by a company requires all employees and stakeholders in the company to adopt the code of ethics. The handbook of the UK Financial Services Authority (FSA) probably goes further than most in legalizing a broad range of macro compliance concepts requiring firms:

[...] to conduct their business with integrity, to take reasonable care to organize and control their affairs responsibly and effectively, with adequate risk management systems and to observe proper standards of market conduct (Pratt, 2008, pp. 184-6).

The FSA principles are commendable but they expect firms to comply and to behave according to this set of principles. However, compliance is an objective that can only be attained with effective enforcement. Both Rossi (2010) and Demidenko and McNutt (2010) examine the role of compliance and responsibility in modern businesses today, wherein there is a narrow sense of compliance and responsibility in modern businesses today, wherein there is a narrow sense of compliance defined in terms of policies and procedures and process within a company. The special issue discusses a broader view of what constitutes compliance as a form of corporate governance mandated by a code of ethical practice, wherein duties are ascribed to each individual and wherein each individual, employee and stakeholder has a duty to fulfill. The governance objectives are defined by a code of ethics and not by an ethos of accountability.

In our daily lives, some of us have a sense of moral responsibility. Moral law is obeyed because it is the right thing to do. For some it is a matter of religious faith and for others it is a matter of

rational self-interest. If we argue that society has no inherent rights over an individual then a random individual may be observed acting morally because he or she is bound by and respects the constraints or rules or laws in society, for example, law against murder. Equally a random individual is bounded by choice- he or she does not have to give Tk.500 to charity if they do not wish to do so. Kant's rule-based ethics is independent of the consequences, his morality is not the same as self-interest and one is acting morally when one performs one's duty. Whatever the merit of Kant's philosophy within the schools of philosophy, a debate is required in the business world in order to achieve a better understanding of individual responsibility and duties required, and accountability with a company.

This work concentrates on the discussing about corporate social responsibilities and its importance. Here, we also try to make an integrative framework to apply Kant's philosophy which will provide a template to consider issues in corporate governance from the perspective of morality, justice, virtue and politics.

Objectives:

The main objective of this paper is to make an inquest of the corporate social responsibility focusing its importance and how Kant's philosophy use as a template to consider issues in corporate governance from the perspective of morality, justice, virtue and politics. One of the motivation for this paper is to articulate the overall CSR concepts and application of Kant's philosophy in this respective.

Methodology:

The study has been conducted mainly on the basis of literature survey and secondary information. Various journals and research papers, diagnostic study reports and newspaper articles have been surveyed in making this study. Few concerned persons (Academics, Business Man) have been personally consulted with in order to have their thoughts in this issue.

Definition of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR):

Frederick (2006) summarizes what CSR meant in the 1950s into three core ideas:

1. the idea of corporate managers as public trustees;
2. the idea of balancing competing claims to corporate resources; and
3. the acceptance of philanthropy as a manifestation of business's support of good causes.

Keith Davis (1960) argued that some decisions made by businessmen bore in mind their social responsibility. Another author that contributed to the conceptual evolution of social

responsibility in the 1960s was Joseph McGuire (1963). In his book *Business and Society*, he posited that social responsibility urges corporations to assume certain responsibilities to society, which extend beyond their economic and legal obligations.

Milton Friedman (1962) presented an opposite view to McGuire (1963), stating that CSR subverts its own order when it denies the principle of maximization of profit set by the capitalist system. He affirmed that “few trends would so thoroughly undermine the very foundations of our free society as the acceptance by corporate officials of a social responsibility other than to make as much money for their shareholders as they possibly can”. (Friedman, 1962, p.133).

CSR has been variously defined as:

An organization’s obligation to maximize its positive impact and minimize its negative effects in being a contributing member to society, with concern for society’s long-run needs and wants. CSR means being a good steward of society’s economic and human resources (Journal of Consumer Marketing, 2001).

The obligations of the firm to its stakeholders-people and groups who can affect or a who are affected by

Corporate policies and practices. These obligations go beyond legal requirements and the company’s duties to its shareholders. Fulfillment of these obligations is intended to minimize any harm and maximize the long-run beneficial impact of the firm on society (Bloom and Gundlach, 2001, p. 142).

The intelligent and objective concern for the welfare of society that restrains individual and corporate behavior from ultimately destructive activities, no matter how immediately profitable, and leads in the direction of positive contributions to human betterment, variously as the latter may be defined (Andrews, quoted in Hartman, 1998, p. 243).

In summary, CSR entails the obligation stemming from the implicit “social contract” between business and society for firms to be responsive to society’s long-run needs and wants, optimizing the positive effects and minimizing the negative effects of its actions on society.

Popular perspectives on business’ role in society:

Table 1 shows a spectrum of opinions regarding the appropriate role of business in society. At one end are those who say business only has an economic responsibility to make a profit while obeying the law (the pure profit-making view or economic CSR). In the middle are people who simply want corporate management to be more sensitive to the social impact of their decisions, especially regarding potential harms to stakeholders (the socially aware view or ethical CSR). At the other end of the spectrum are those who want to see corporations actively involved in programs which can ameliorate various social ills, such as by providing employment opportunities for everyone, improving the environment, and promoting worldwide justice, even if it costs the shareholders money (the community service view or altruistic CSR). At one end of the spectrum the basic concern is with economic values such as productivity and efficiency, while avoiding social involvement. At the other end of the spectrum the primary concern is societal welfare even at the expense of profits (Miller and Ahrens, 1993).

Author	Position on business' role in society
Albert Carr	Pure profit-making view- economic CSR: business has lower standards of ethics than society and no social responsibility other than obedience to the law.
Milton Friedman	Constrained profit-making view- economic CSR: business should maximize shareholder wealth, obey the law, and be ethical.
R. Edward Freeman	Socially aware view- ethical CSR: Business should be sensitive to be potential harms of its actions on various stakeholder groups.
Archie Carroll	Community service view/corporate social performance perspective- altruistic CSR: business must use its vast resources for social good.

Table 1 Spectrum of viewpoints on the role of business in society.

Another way of envisioning the spectrum is that at one end is property rights theory- the corporation is viewed as the private property of its stockholders, while at the other end – the social institution theory- the firm is considered a public institution sanctioned by the state for some social good (Boatright, 1999). A moderate and relatively recent view which now dominates thinking in financial economics and public law- the contractual theory of the firm holds that a company's assets are provided by many groups in addition to shareholders, such as employees,

customers, suppliers, and the like, and so the company arises from the property rights and right of contract of every corporate constituency, not just stockholders (Boatright, 1999).

Ethical CSR:

Ethical CSR involves fulfilling the firm's ethical duties. This is "social responsibility" in the sense that a corporation is morally responsible to any individuals or groups where it might inflict actual or potential injury (physical, mental, economic, spiritual and emotional) from a particular course of action. Even when the two parties to a transaction are not harmed others parties (stakeholders) might be.

Any organization not adhering to its ethical responsibilities would be acting as a morally irresponsible agent. Although harms cannot always be avoided, they should be minimized where feasible. For example, when a company decides to close or relocate a plant because the product is no longer selling or the source of raw materials has changed, this would seem sound. While the shift might cause temporary difficulties for some employees and their community, it makes more efficient use of resources and therefore, benefits society as a whole, i.e. it is the socially responsible thing to do so long as injuries to workers are minimized as much as reasonably possible via means such as advance notification and severance pay.

Ethical edicts must be adhered to even at the firm's expense in terms of possible foregone profits since by definition, ethics deals with moral standards that override self-interest. Sometimes actions need to be taken because they are right, not because they are profitable (Chewning *et al.*, 1990; Goodpaster, 1996; Miller and Ahrens, 1993). Managers of a corporation do not have an obligation to maximize profits for shareholders without regard to the means used. As in all social responsibility decisions, there are tradeoffs, and with ethical CSR it is often between short-run profitability and moral actions. For instance, money spent on product safety or pollution control might reduce shareholder profits, but the alternative is to threaten unethically the welfare of others in society (Boatright, 1999).

In fact, responsibility has been described as "the cornerstone of ethics" (Solomon, 1994, p. 114). The term suggests both accountability and usually a position of trust and authority (Solomon, 1994).

In addition to the proper role of business as an institution, we also need to investigate the societal role of professionals, as business managers are generally considered professionals in their fields. In order to do this, we need to distinguish general duties from special duties. General duties or

civic responsibilities are widely accepted ethical requirements for how people should treat one another in a civilized society. They are a kind of cement to the implied social contract that people in society all have with one another. Examples include, “Do no harm” (ethical CSR) and “If possible, do good” (altruistic CSR). Special duties are situational- we are required to do something given our circumstances. Managers and professionals are said to have special duties due to their privileged position within society.

Altruistic CSR:

Altruistic or humanitarian CSR is Carroll’s “fourth face” of CSR- philanthropic responsibilities- to be a “good corporate citizen” by “giving back” to society, furthering some social good, regardless of whether the firm will financially reap what it has spiritually sown. It demands that corporations help alleviate “public welfare deficiencies” (Brenkert, 1996, p.525), such as urban blight, drug and alcohol problems, poverty, crime, illiteracy, lack of sufficient funding for educational institutions, inadequate moneys for the arts, chronic unemployment and other social ills within a community or society. The business has no “moral obligations”, only alleged “social obligations” (DeGeorge, 1990, p. 168). Humanitarian CSR is based on capability responsibility- the company has the resources to be able to do social good.

A final and purely pragmatic argument for humanitarian CSR is enlightened capitalism. Being socially responsible does not necessarily mean profits will fall- indeed, they might rise because of the favorable publicity and goodwill, enhanced employee morale leading to higher productivity, and less government intervention, which historically has led to excessive power, tyranny, corruption and abuse of rights (Novak, 1996). However, if business prospers, this we are discussing strategic CSR, nor altruistic CSR.

In short, all of the pro-altruistic CSR arguments really only hold for ethical CSR or strategic CSR. There is no foundation for the firm acting out of purely benevolent motives.

Kantian dialectic:

Kant’s philosophy provides a template to consider issues in corporate governance from the perspective of morality, justice, virtue and politics. Kant casts his influence far beyond academia and different commentators question his morality. Our objective in this issue is to open a debate on the relevance of Kantian scholarship as template for establishing an ethical code of corporate governance, which will ultimately ensure proper corporate social responsibility practices in this particular area.

Kant argued that the highest good was the good will. To act from a good will is to act from duty. Thus, it is the intention behind an action rather than its consequences that make that action good. For example, for Kant if a businessman is honest so as to earn a good reputation, these acts of being honest are not genuinely moral. The businessman is only truly moral if he or she is honest because being honest is right (one's duty). Person's of good will do their duty because it is their duty and for no other reason.

Kant distinguished between two kinds of duty (imperatives). Sometimes we do something so than we may get something else. We go to work to earn money or study to earn good grades. If you want good grades, you ought to study. Kant referred to this kind of duty as a hypothetical imperative because it is of the form if you want to do x, do y. The duty to study is dependent on your desire for good grades.

Other duties are required per se, with no ifs, ands or buts. Kant described these duties as categorical and referred to the fundamental principle of ethics as the categorical imperative. He believed that reason provided the basis for the categorical imperative, thus the categorical imperative of morality were requirements of reason. Although Kant spoke of "the" categorical imperative, he formulated it in many ways. Most commentators focus on three formulations:

1. An action has moral worth if it is done for the sake of duty. (DUTY)
2. An action is morally correct if its maxim can be willed as a universal law. (UNIVERSALIZABILITY)
3. We should always treat humanity, whether in ourselves or other people, as an end in itself and never merely as means to an end. (Respect)

Kant believed that only human beings can follow laws of their own choosing (i.e. act rationally). Human beings are the only creatures that are free, and it is the fact that we are free that enables us to be rational and moral. Our free will is what gives us our dignity and unconditioned worth.

Kant's ethics then is an ethics of duty rather than an ethics of consequences. The ethical person is the person who acts from the right intentions. We are able to act in this way because we have free will. The fundamental principle of ethics, the categorical imperative, is a requirement of reason and is binding on all rational beings. These are the essentials of Kant's ethics. Let us see how apply, specially, to business ethics.

Self-Defeating Immoral Business Practice: Kant's first formulation of the categorical imperative is "Act only on that maxim by which you can at the same time will that it should

become a universal law.” But the problem with the Golden Rule is that so long as you are willing to let others treat you in an immoral way, it seems as if you are allowed to treat them immorally as well. Albert Carr provided the classic statement of this position regarding business in a 1968 Harvard Business Review article:

We live in what is probably the most competitive of the world’s civilized societies. Our customs encourage a high degree of aggression in the individual’s striving for success. Business is our main area of competition and it has been ritualized into a game of strategy... That most businessmen are not indifferent to ethics in their private lives, everyone will agree. My point is that in their office lives they cease to be private citizens; they become game players who must be guided by a different set of standards—The golden rule for all its value as an ideal for society is simply not feasible as a guide for business. A good part of the time the businessman is trying to do to others as he hopes others will not do unto him.

Carr’s also mentioned in his article that the game of business most resembles to Poker. He also mentioned that Poker’s own brand of ethics different from civilized human relationship which calls for distrust of the other fellow. It also ignores the claim of friendship. Carr’s article provoked a tremendous business response, much of it negative. However, there are many indications that Carr’s position or positions close to it are widely held in business world. As a people of business, we know that cynicism about business ethics is widespread. Moreover, surprising number of companies that had served as icons of morally responsible behavior have, as a result of ethical missteps, fallen off their pedestals. Moreover, Rana Plaza collapse, fire accident at Tazreen Fashion Ltd, fire at FR Tower etc. was caused by misconduct of Business People has added to the cynicism about the ethics of business practice.

Both cynicism about business ethics and actual business misconduct are dangerous to capitalism. One of the strengths of Immanuel Kant’s moral theory is that he can avoid the weakness of the Golden Rule described earlier and show that immoral business practice is irrational. Now, we will try to spell out Kant’s argument and some of its implications.

As Kant says,

And could I say to myself that everyone may make a false promise when he is in difficulty from which he cannot escape? Immediately I see that I could will the lie but not a universal law to lie.

For with such a law there would be no promises at all, inasmuch as it would be futile to make a pretense of my intention in regard to future actions to those who would not believe this pretense or- if they over hastily did so- would pay me back in my own coin. Thus my maxim would necessarily destroy itself as soon as it was made a universal law.

The general point to be made from Kant's discussion of the immorality of lying is that self-contradictory universalized maxims are morally prohibited. That is why it is wrong to break promise; the maxim for that action could not be consistently universalized.

Kant wants to show that some principles (maxims) on which actions are based are inconsistent or self-defeating. It is impossible for everyone to act on the basis of the principle; that is why the principle cannot be accepted as universal law. If an individual acted on a principle that it would be impossible for everyone to follow, that individual's action would be wrong.

Thus the categorical imperative functions as a test to see if the principle (maxim) on which an action is based is morally permissible. So long as the principle for one's action passes the test of the categorical imperative, the action may be undertaken. A business manager who accepts Kantian morality would ask, for any decision, whether the principle on which the decision is based passes the test of the categorical imperative. If it does, then the decision would be morally permissible.

The making of promises is a practice. It is important to note with Christine Korsgaard that the self-contradiction interpretation of the categorical imperative works well for the violation of the rules of a practice. "[A] practice has a standard purpose and if its rules are universally violated it ceases to be efficacious for this person, and so ceases to exist." Since business consists, at least in part, of a number of practices with standard purposes, we might expect Kant's universal law formulation of the categorical imperative to work well in business- and so it does.

Management theorists have discovered trust because trust is now seen as an important ingredient for competitive success. Management theorists seem to be endorsing the following hypothetical imperative:

If one wants to achieve profitability in one's business, then one must establish trust with one's various corporate stakeholders.

What we need to do is transform a prudential argument for trust into an ethical obligation required by the categorical imperative. What needs to be shown is that business practice requires trust, so that one who acts in ways that violate trust or make trust on the part of others impossible is pragmatically (volitionally) inconsistent. With respect to showing the inconsistency, Korsgaard is once again instructive:

We must find some purpose or purposes which belong essentially to the will, and in the world where maxims that fail these tests are universal law, these essential purposes will be thwarted, because the means of achieving them will be unavailable.

Korsgaard's insight here can be helpful as we transform the prudential argument for trust into a categorical imperative. Eventually we argue that trust is essential in most business relationships if business is to achieve its ends. But first the prudential end of profit-making must be seen as an ethical obligation. The first step is to claim that

1. A manager has a contractual obligation to manage the firm in the best interests of the corporation.
2. A manager can manage the firm in the best interests of the corporation only if he/she builds trusts among the corporate stakeholders.
3. Therefore, a manager has an obligation to build trust among the corporate stakeholders.

The first statement is a normative claim regarding the obligation of managers. Since the manager has made a promise (has a contractual obligation) to manage in the best interest of the corporation, and since building trusting relationships among the corporate stakeholders is necessary to fulfill that promise, then a manager has a moral obligation and not merely a prudential one for building those trusting relationships.

Francis Fukuyama provides another argument to show that trust is essential in business: It is perhaps easier to appreciate the economic value of trust if we consider what a world devoid of trust would look like. If we had to approach every contract with the assumption that our partners would try to cheat us if they could, then we would have to spend a considerable amount of time bulletproofing the document to make sure that there were no legal loopholes by which we could be taken advantage of. Contracts would be endlessly long, spelling out every possible contingency, and defining every possible obligation.

In passing it should be noted that it is impossible to spell out every possible contingency or to define every possible obligation. What Fukuyama is drawing attention to is the transaction costs in doing business and pointing out that in the absence of trust, the transaction costs would become so high that commercial transactions as we know them would become prohibitively expensive.

As a Kantian, it is important to point out that Fukuyama's argument is not simply consequentialist. It is not simply the case that a lack of trust or decline in trust leads to bad consequences, although it does. Rather, Fukuyama's argument is a Kantian argument to the effect that a market to some extent rests on trust. As there is less and less trust, you reach a point where the necessity to use lawyers to write detailed contracts imposes transactions costs such that economic transactions do not resemble a market at all. Undermining trust undermines the market itself.

So far we have argued that maxims that undermine trust are pragmatically self-contradictory. But maxims that support trust can be morally required as well. The first step is to argue that trust provides a firm with a competitive advantage. Now, it is a "law" of economics that, other things being equal, a firm with a competitive advantage will triumph over its competitors. Or to put it another way, other things being equal, to adopt a maxim not to trust when trusting provides competitive advantage is to undermine the survival of the firm. If trusting is necessary to the survival of the firm and protecting the survival of the firm is a contractual obligation for the managers, then the managers is obligated to support trusting relationships among the firm's stakeholders.

1. **Treating Stakeholder with Respect:** Since human beings have free will and thus are able to act from laws required by reason. Kant believed they have dignity or a value beyond price. Thus, one human being cannot use another simply to satisfy his or her own

interests. This is the core insight behind Kant's second formulation of the categorical imperative. "Always treat the humanity in a person as an end and never as a means merely."

Kant did not simply assert that human beings are entitled to respect; he has an elaborate argument for it. Human beings ought to be respected because human beings have dignity. And further, the denial of dignity is what makes much downsizing unjust. In these cases, that which is without price- human beings –are treated as simply exchangeable with that which has a price. Human employees have a dignity that machines and capital do not. Thus, it looks like managers cannot manage their corporate resources in the most efficient manner without violating the respect-for-persons principle. Whether that is the correct implication remains to be seen.

But first, why do persons possess a dignity that is beyond all prices? They have dignity because human beings are capable of autonomy and thus are capable of self-governance. As autonomous beings capable of self-governance, they are also responsible beings, since autonomy and self-governance; they are also responsible beings, since autonomy and self-governance are conditions for responsibility. A person who is not autonomous and who is not capable of self-governance is not responsible. That's why little children or the mentally ill are not considered responsible beings. Thus, there is a conceptual link between being a human being, being an autonomous being, being capable of self-governance, and being a responsible being.

The first step to respecting the humanity in a person requires that a person should not be used as a means only. With respect to business ethics, this means that a business relationship should be neither coerced nor deceptive. The general point against coercion and deception has been made by Korsgaard:

According to the Formula of Humanity, coercion and deception are the most fundamental forms of wrongdoing to others- the roots of all evil. Coercion and deception violate the conditions of possible assent, and all actions which depend for their nature and efficacy

on their coercive or deceptive character are ones that others cannot assent to ... Physical coercion treats someone's person as a tool; lying treats someone's reason as a tool. That is why Kant finds it so horrifying; it is a direct violation of autonomy.

Kant's point about the immorality of coercion and deception is accepted by nearly all regardless of their political persuasion. Coercion and deception are a violation of one's negative freedom because they block a person from choosing ends she would have chosen had the coercion or deception not occurred.

Economic actions are considered free actions entered into voluntarily. If both parties are fully informed, then business transactions are neither coerced nor involve deception. They thus pass the two tests for negative freedom. Using the standard assumption that the employment relationship is a contractual one and further assuming that the employee has all the relevant knowledge regarding the relationship, one could argue that the employee has accepted the fact that if the price of machinery becomes cheaper compared to the price of labor, then he has agreed that the manager is morally permitted to substitute a machine for his labor. This is because one could say that employees know that they can be laid off if their labor becomes more expensive compared to machines. They accept the job knowing that, and thus here is a sense in which layoffs are something that has been agreed to. The employees are not used as a means merely because they have freely consented to the conditions of their employment. There is neither coercion nor deception, and thus the employees have not been used.

Lack of coercion and deception is not always sufficient for treating those in a business relationship with respect. On occasion we are obliged to act positively to further their humanity. This is because we not only must not use people but we must treat them as ends in themselves. To treat a person as an end itself sometimes requires that we do more than merely refrain from coercion or deception; it requires that we take some positive action to help a person. This is required both by the respect-for-persons formulation of the categorical imperative, by some of Kant's own writings on work, and by Kant's imperfect duty of beneficence to help others.

The argument that a business firm can honor its obligation to treat employees as an end through meaningful work rests of Kant's characterization as an end through meaningful work rests of Kant's characterization of positive freedom. The Kant scholar who has most persuasively

articulated the Kantian theory of positive freedom is Thomas E.Hill, Jr. As we said earlier, negative freedom for Kant is the ability to act independently of determination by alien causes. Negative freedom is freedom from. Positive freedom is the freedom to achieve something. An uneducated person may not be coerced but needs education to be truly free. In terms of respect, the uneducated person needs education to gain the autonomy that goes with full respect.

The task before us is to show how the meaningful work requirement is an obvious and appropriate way to have business be supportive of each employee's positive freedom. In so doing, we make use of Hill's interpretation of the phrase "humanity as an end in itself". Based on an examination of the Kantian texts, Hill argues that humanity includes the following capacities:

- The capacity and disposition to act on the basis of reasons.
- The capacity to act on principles of prudence and efficiency (hypothetical imperatives) so long as these hypothetical imperatives do not contradict categorical imperatives.
- The power to set any end whatsoever, which includes the "ability to see future consequences, adopt long range goals, resist immediate temptation, and even to commit oneself to ends for which one has no sensuous desire.
- The capacity to accept categorical imperatives.
- "Some ability to understand the world and to reason abstractly."

Assuming that Hill is right, it is a requirement of morality that people treat other people in ways that respect these capabilities, for that is what Kant means by treating humanity as an end in itself.

Before applying Kant's imperative regarding treating humanity as an end in itself, a few more clarifying textual comments are necessary. What is the nature of our positive duty to promote the happiness of others or- in our more restricted language – to promote the happiness of others or – in our more restricted language- to promote the positive freedom of another? Kant believed it is an imperfect duty in the sense that we do not need to help another on every occasion it is possible to do so.

Let us apply all this to the business firm. Employers must not coerce (violate the negative freedom) of their employees; this duty is a perfect one. Moreover, employers have an imperfect duty to adopt a maxim to be concerned with the positive freedom of their employees, that is, with their moral well-being and physical welfare. Of special concern are the rational capacities identified by Hill. Management practice should be such that it strengthens, rather than weakens, the rational capacities of employees.

So, adopting the maxim of providing positive freedom for employees can be honored if the employers provide *meaningful work*. This is because spelling out the content of positive freedom as we have done here provides a reasonable account of the normative conditions for meaningful work. Considering Kantian theory, meaningful work can be set out as follows:

- Meaningful work is work that is freely chosen and provides opportunities for the worker to exercise autonomy on the job.
- The work relationship must support the autonomy and rationality of human beings. Work that unnecessarily deadens autonomy or that undermines rationality is immoral.
- Meaningful work is work that provides a salary sufficient for the worker to exercise her independence and provides for her physical well-being and the satisfaction of some of her desires.
- Meaningful work is work that enables a person to develop her rational capacities.
- Meaningful work is work that does not interfere with a person's moral development.
- Meaningful work is work that is not paternalistic in the sense of interfering with the worker's conception of how he/she wishes to obtain happiness.

Kant argues that work is necessary for the development of selfhood:

Life is the faculty of spontaneous activity, the awareness of all our human powers. Occupation gives us this awareness... without occupation man cannot live happily. If he earns his bread, he eats it with greater pleasure than if it is doled out to him..... Man feels more contented after heavy work than when he has done no work; for by work he has set his powers in motion.

Thus, it appears that work is a duty that one has to oneself. It contributes to independence and to our self-conception. Although Kant does not say so explicitly, one can infer from his remarks that working provides self-respect.

In addition, Kant actually endorses wealth and the pleasure it brings. However, to work simply in order to earn money is to display the vice of miserliness, a vice that is even worse than avarice. So long as work is required to make money so that one can provide for one's needs and pleasures, and in so doing make oneself independent, work has value. Selected comments of Kant's will establish his view.

A man whose possessions are sufficient for his needs is well-to-do... All wealth is means.. for satisfying the owner's wants, free purposes and inclinations BY dependence on others, man loses in worth, and so a man of independent means is an object of respect...But the miser finds a direct pleasure in money itself, although money is nothing but a pure means.... The spendthrift is a lovable simpleton; the miser is a detestable fool. The former has not destroyed his better self and might face the misfortune that awaits him with courage, but the latter is a man of poor character.

So long as business firms provide jobs that provide sufficient wealth, they contribute to the independence and thus to the self-respect of persons. For a Kantian, the true contribution of capitalism would be that it provides jobs that help provide self-respect.

In summary, We have tried to apply to the business context the message of the second formulation of the categorical imperative to treat the humanity in a person as an end in itself and never as a means merely. To do that a firm must treat all its corporate stakeholders in a non-coercive and non-deceptive manner. We have also shown how management commitment to practices that provide meaningful work as we have defined it here is a plausible way to not just respect employees but to treat them in ways that enhance their positive freedom. In the context of business, meaningful work is a means to self-actualization. We have developed a concept of meaningful work consistent with Kantianism and tried to show how good management practice can be supportive of this Kantian vision of meaningful work. Thus Kant's ethics can inspire business firms to feats more noble than merely making money.

The Firm as a Moral Community: The third formulation of the categorical imperative is usually called the kingdom-of-ends formulation. Loosely put, this formulation of the categorical imperative says that you should act as if you were a member of an ideal kingdom of ends in which you were both subject and sovereign at the same time.

What did Kant mean? Kant recognized that human beings interacted with other human beings (ends). The arena of interaction was called the kingdom of ends. A business organization, like any other organization, is composed of individual persons, and since persons are moral creatures, the interaction of persons in an organization is constrained by the categorical imperative. This means that an organization, whatever its purpose, should be governed by morality. Because an organization is a community of persons, whatever else an organization is, it should be a moral community. As Kant said,

For all rational beings stand under the law that each of them should treat himself and all others never merely as a means but in every case also as an end in himself. Thus there arises a systematic union of rational beings through common objective laws. This is a realm which may be called a realm of ends.. because what these laws have in view is just the relation of these beings to each other as ends and means.

Whereas social scientists would look for the natural laws that govern these interactions (organizational behavior), moral philosophers would seek those norms that should govern such interactions. However, those moral norms include far more than the statements of the categorical imperative.

What Kant suggests is that we ask moral beings to act from laws that are publicly acceptable in the sense that they can be objective for every rational being. If the laws are publicly acceptable, then one can be both sovereign and subject with respect to moral laws- subject because one is bound to obey them and sovereign because they are laws of one's own choosing. Let us apply this to business. Since all persons in economic affairs are moral agents, they are equal with respect to possessing dignity and intrinsic value. Thus, in a business firm, organized as a moral community, the interests of every member of the community are equal to the interests of every other member.

If one were to take a Kantian moral perspective, the following principles of corporate policies and procedures would be appropriate and management would be on sound moral ground in following them.

Principles of a Moral Firm

- The firm should consider the interests of all the affected stakeholders in any decision it makes.
- The firm should have those affected by the firm's policies and procedures participate in the determination of those policies and procedures or have a means for endorsing those policies and principles before they are implemented.
- It should not be the case that for all decisions, the interests of one stakeholder take priority.
- When a situation arises where it appears that the interests of one set of stakeholders must be sacrificed for the interests of another set of stakeholders, that decision cannot be made on the grounds that there are a greater number of stakeholders in one group than in another.
- No principle or process can be adopted that is inconsistent in the sense explained in the discussion of the universalizability formulation of the categorical imperative. In addition, no principle or process can violate the humanity in the person of any stakeholder as explained in the discussion of the respect for persons formulation of the categorical imperative.
- The managers in every profit-making firm have an imperfect duty of beneficence to practice corporate social responsibility.
- Each business firm must establish procedures to ensure that relations among stakeholders are governed by the rules of justice or fairness.

We think the rationale for most of these principles can be derived from the explanation of Kant's ethics already provided. Principle 1 seems like a straightforward requirement for any moral theory that takes respect for persons seriously. Since autonomy is what makes humans worthy of respect, a commitment to principle 2 required. Principle 3 provides a kind of organizational legitimacy; it ensures that those involved in the firm receive some minimum benefits from being a part of it. Principle 4 rules out utilitarianism as a criterion for decision-making in the moral

firm. The justification for principle 6 is based on an extension of the individual's imperfect obligation of beneficence which Kant defended in the *Metaphysics of Morals*. There Kant (1994, p. 52) says:

That beneficence is a duty results from the fact that since out self-love cannot be separated from our need to be loved by others (to obtain help from them in the case of need), we thereby make ourselves an end for others... hence the happiness of others is an end which is at the same time a duty.

The strategy here is to extend this argument to the corporate level. If corporations have benefited from society, they have a duty of beneficence to society in return. And corporations have benefited. Society protects corporations by providing the means for enforcing business contracts. Finally, principle 7 is a procedural principle designed to ensure that whatever rules the corporation adopts conform to the basic principles of justice.

A Kantian views an organization as a moral community. Each member of the organization stands in a moral relationship to all others. On one hand, the managers of a business firm should respect the humanity in all persons in the organization. On the other hand, each individual in a business firm, managed as a Kantian moral community, should view the organization other than purely instrumentally, that is, as merely a means for achieving individual goals. Organizations are created as ways of achieving common goals and shared ends. An individual who views the organization purely instrumentally is acting contrary to the "respect for persons" principle.

A manager who adopts the Kantian principles of a moral firm must also look at human nature in a certain way. In management terms, the theory Y view of human nature must be adopted rather than a theory X view. (The distinction between theory X and theory Y was made prominent by McGregor (1960). Theory X assumed that people had an inherent dislike of work and would avoid it if possible. It also assumed that the average person seeks to avoid responsibility. Theory Y assumes the opposite: those employees prefer to act imaginatively and creatively and are willing to assume responsibility. Although we can debate about which theory is descriptively more accurate, as a normative matter a Kantian manager should adopt theory Y. For it is theory Y that views human beings as having the dignity Kant thinks they deserved. Moreover, both theory X and theory Y have the tendency to become self-fulfilling prophecies. By that I mean that people will tend to behave as they are treated. If a manger treats people in accordance with theory X, employees will tend to behave as theory X predicts. Conversely with theory Y, Thus

the question becomes what kind of organization should the manager and the employees, working together, create. For the Kantian, the answer is clear. People should try to create an organization where the participants in the organization behave as theory Y would predict. People should seek to create an organization where members develop their rational and moral capacities, including the capacity to take responsibility.

Conclusion

Responsibility and consistency (characterized as a nonappearance of responsibility) have been the corridor sign of corporate "misgovernance" during the previous decade as the couple of are considered responsible for the failings in an administration framework that has been without a moral establishment. Morals, lamentably, has been divided a corporate cycle and marked as CSR however duty essentially must be disconnected from its notable linkage to CSR and migrated into its philosophical system and good compass. Corporate administration has been characterized in term of straightforwardness and consistency – it requires a moral establishment. The thinking in Kantianism is best perceived as thinking from obligation. As people we are committed to make the wisest decision, that they are good laws that unmistakably characterize what is correct and what's up. It is focal fundamental of Kant's ethical way of thinking that an activity is just genuinely good in the event that it is ethically persuaded. Genuinely good activities can't be polluted by thought processes of personal circumstance.

Kantian methodology can play an edge of reference to comprehend the obligation of an individual just as regard to others which at last establish a climate where CSR will be polished from mindfulness. Since so far all we have demonstrated is that Kant's emphasis on the virtue of an ethical thought process has not made his hypothesis insignificant to business morals. Yet, maybe his emphasis on the virtue of the ethical rationale has a positive commitment to make to business morals and isn't just an obstruction to be survived. Maybe zeroing in on issues other than benefits, for example, significant work for representatives, a vote based work place, non-tricky publicizing, and a non-coercive relationship with providers will really upgrade the primary concern. Be that as it may, maybe oddly, benefits can be upgraded in the event that we don't zero in so solely on the primary concern. To place this in more Kantian terms, maybe benefits will be upgraded if the director centers around regarding the mankind in the individual of the multitude of corporate partners.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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